

Newsletter #9

March 2026

AI-PROGNOSIS -

Towards Parkinson's risk assessment and prognosis through AI

Newsletter highlights

How AI is Enabling Earlier and More Personalised Healthcare

Scientific Publications

Knowledge Base

Events

Learn more on www.ai-prognosis.eu

Funded by the European Union

AI-PROGNOSIS receives funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101080581.

Project Updates

How AI is Enabling Earlier and More Personalised Healthcare

A new joint video highlights how AI can support earlier prediction and personalise care across multiple diseases

What happens when a disease enters someone's life and changes everything? Millions of people live with conditions that shape their daily routines – often in ways that are invisible to others. Early diagnosis, timely intervention and better care can make a profound difference.

This is where **AI-PROGNOSIS**, together with the EU-funded projects **iPROLEPSIS** and **REBECCA**, contributes to a shared vision of how artificial intelligence and digital biomarkers can enable earlier prediction, continuous monitoring and more personalised, patient-centred care **across Parkinson's disease, psoriatic arthritis, and breast cancer**.

Our new joint video, developed under the **European Commission's Booster Service**, highlights how real-world behavioural data, wearable signals and patient-reported information can be transformed into actionable clinical insights – helping clinicians make more informed decisions while keeping patients at the centre of care.

Watch the video [here](#)

To learn more about each initiative and their work:

iPROLEPSIS - www.iprolepsis.eu

AI-PROGNOSIS - www.ai-prognosis.eu

REBECCA - www.rebeccaproject.eu

Scientific Publications

Recent research outputs from the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium

Rizou V., et al. Scientific Reports. 2025; 15:41931
doi: 10.1038/s41598-025-25812-9

Read the [full publication](#)

PDualNet: a deep learning framework for joint prediction of Parkinson's disease progression subtype and MDS-UPDRS scores

Chatzis T., et al. 2025 IEEE International Conference on E-health Networking, Application & Services (Healthcom), 21-23 Oct. 2025, Abu Dhabi

Read the [full publication](#)

A Deep Learning Approach for Parkinsonian Tremor Assessment Using Wearables

Moustaklis A., et al. 2025 IEEE International Conference on E-health Networking, Application & Services (Healthcom), 21-23 Oct. 2025, Abu Dhabi

Read the [full publication](#)

On capturing effects of medication change in Parkinson's disease with wrist accelerometry-based digital biomarkers

Gerasimou I., et al. 47th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC 2025), Copenhagen, Denmark, 14-18 July 2025

Read the [full publication](#)

Wrist Accelerometry-based Digital Assessment of Slowness of Movement in Parkinson's Disease: a Multi-Cohort Analysis

Knowledge Base

Educational resources from the AI-PROGNOSIS Learning Hub

The AI-PROGNOSIS Learning Hub offers educational resources to raise awareness about Parkinson's disease and the role of artificial intelligence in its diagnosis and care.

Articles

Explore the [articles](#)

Our articles exploring different stages of Parkinson's disease and the role of artificial intelligence in diagnosis and care are now available in **multiple languages - English, German, Spanish and French.**

Topics include:

Predicting Parkinson's Progression with AI

Promise and Pitfalls - exploring how AI models aim to anticipate disease progression.

Using AI to Strengthen Parkinson's Diagnosis

How artificial intelligence may support earlier and more accurate detection.

Living with Parkinson's Disease

Insights into daily life with Parkinson's and how treatment and care can support quality of life.

Journey to a Parkinson's Diagnosis

Understanding how Parkinson's is diagnosed and why the process can take time.

New quiz

Test your knowledge with our new quiz "AI and Early Detection of Parkinson's" and learn how artificial intelligence may help identify early signs of Parkinson's disease using digital health data.

Take the [quiz](#)

Events

Recent outreach and dissemination activities

AI-PROGNOSIS Project Presented to MSc Students

17 January 2026

Beatriz Alves (FMH-ULisboa) presented the **AI-PROGNOSIS** project to MSc students in Advanced Practice of Neurological Physiotherapy at the Health School of the Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal, Portugal.

The presentation took place within the curricular unit Technology Allied to Neurological Physiotherapy and focused on communicating the overall context, objectives, and scope of the project. It also highlighted how artificial intelligence is being applied within the project to support Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis.

MDS Course on AI and Movement Disorders

12 December 2025

AI-PROGNOSIS was presented during the MDS course "Advances in Technology and Artificial Intelligence Applications in Movement Disorders", a live-streamed international educational event.

During the lecture "Wearables and Video Analysis for Parkinson's Disease and other Movement Disorders", **Dr Margherita Fabbri (CHU de Toulouse)** presented the AI-PROGNOSIS project and highlighted how wearable sensors and video-based analysis can support the digital assessment and monitoring of Parkinson's disease.

The presentation also addressed the role of artificial intelligence in extracting clinically meaningful information from real-world patient data and its potential to support patient-centred care.

Webinar “Parkinson’s Disease and Artificial Intelligence – What does AI mean for those of us living with Parkinson’s?”

25 November 2025

Uppsala University organised a webinar titled “Parkinson’s Disease and Artificial Intelligence – What Does AI Mean for Those Living with Parkinson’s?”, bringing together people living with Parkinson’s disease to discuss how artificial intelligence may support care and daily life.

The session was led by a person living with Parkinson’s and facilitated by the AI-PROGNOSIS team. The project was presented as an example of how AI can be applied to support Parkinson’s disease research and patient-centred innovation.

The webinar was attended by **55 participants** and included an **interactive Q&A** and **live polling** to gather participants’ views on the role of AI in Parkinson’s disease.

Participants raised questions about topics such as predicting disease progression, alternative ways to communicate when tremor affects phone use, speech-to-text and voice or eye-tracking technologies, memory training and reminder tools, and the use of large patient registries to gain deeper insights into Parkinson’s disease.

Participants’ views (n=55) on AI in Parkinson’s disease:

69%

positive about AI for Parkinson’s disease

15%

AI is promising but not yet applicable

13%

uncertain about AI role

0%

negative views about AI

Feedback from the discussion will help inform the further development of educational materials and patient-centred AI research within the project.

